
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INDIAN JUDICIARY: ENHANCING JUSTICE OR THREATENING JUDICIAL CONSCIENCE?

Author – Babli Dhakad¹

DOI:

Abstract

Indian judiciary is handling trust of over 1.47 billion people. The integration of Artificial Intelligence(AI) into judicial systems has evolved as a transformative development in modern legal administration. The enjoyment of benefits that AI gives are abundant from advancement in document preparation to establishment of e-courts. But at the same time emergence of AI leads to disturbance in core spirit of law that is justice delivery. The open use of technology in fields where manual input is required tends to change the output. At present, there is no such rules and regulations that can regulate the use of AI in judiciary. To guarantee that innovation does not undermine but rather strengthens the Constitution, it is essential to have strong legal frameworks, human involvement, accountable algorithms, and capacity-building institutions. This article aims to provide analytical study about need to regulate AI in judiciary to safeguard constitutional ethics and maintain equity, justice and judicial conscience.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Judiciary, Constitution, Justice, Judicial System

INTRODUCTION

The judiciary is one of the most significant and independent organs of government and is responsible for enforcing laws in India. Many people visit the Supreme Court, High Court, or District and Sessions Court on any particular day in India because the judicial system is known to deliver just results for anyone seeking justice. It is essential that the legal system be easily available, fast, straightforward, transparent, and responsive to the needs of the common people

¹ B.A. LL.B. Student at Faculty of Legal Studies, Mewar University, Email: dhakadbabli02@gmail.com

in order to ensure justice. The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology has emerged in the past few years as a potential remedy that can help change the course of justice delivery forever. With time, the use of technology is increasingly becoming common in the courtroom, ranging from court administration tools, case management, crime prevention, and language accessibility to artificial intelligence in legal research. Some of the longstanding challenges confronting the Indian courts include the need to digitalise the system, case pendency, and language barriers. Machine Learning (ML), Natural Language Processing (NLP), Optical Character Recognition (OCR), and Predictive Analytics are some AI tools that have begun to be implemented to assist in automating tasks, enhancing crime prevention, and case monitoring respectively.

The legal sector has been undergoing transformations thanks to efforts such as the e-Courts Project Phase III, use of AI technology in legal translation, predictive policing, and AI-based legal chatbots, among others. While the implementation of AI poses certain challenges, including those of data security, ethical governance, and legal adaptation, the potential of the technology to transform the Indian legal system is immense. The use of AI tends to change the traditional justice delivery system. However, reliance on artificial intelligence brings up an ethical and constitutional issue. The faith of people in judiciary cannot be knocked down. Artificial Intelligence can only reduce the burden of judiciary but it cannot provide justice without biasness. The true spirit of judiciary will be at risk if burden is transferred to AI. This article aims to provide in depth view on use of AI in Indian judiciary and need to regulate through specific guidelines or any legislation. Through discussions regarding judgments, national trends, and global practice, this paper tries to understand whether AI could be used as freely as being in use and how to cope up with the wide spread misuse of AI in judiciary.

The objectives of this research study are:

- To analyse the role of AI in Indian judiciary.

- To examine constitutional and ethical challenges.
- To evaluate whether AI can coexist with judicial discretion and propose actionable policy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in courts has been extensively studied by various researchers and institutions. It has been reported that AI can be used to create discrimination through algorithmic bias, thereby affecting basic rights such as equality and a fair trial. AI aids in conducting legal research, translating documents, and handling case management systems, thus reducing the burden of courts, based on Indian judicial initiatives like SUVAS, SUPACE, and e-Courts. However, some researchers also pointed out that AI lacks human emotions, ethics, and judicial consciousness. The risks associated with relying on AI-generated information without verifying its authenticity was revealed through international research and incidents such as the *Mata v. Avianca* AI citation controversy. Based on these findings, it may be concluded that AI could aid in enhancing the efficiency of the court but should be appropriately regulated and supervised by humans.

METHODOLOGY

Doctrinal and analytical research is adopted to enhance and provide deep analysis. Primary sources for data collection, including the Constitution of India, Supreme Court judgments, PIB reports, AI related judicial initiatives, and more were used, along with examined research papers, Artificial Intelligence literature, reports. These sources helped us trace both legal developments and the challenges faced by general public.

Material was collected from secondary sources through online databases, government websites, and verified research papers and law journal articles. Once

compiled, the sources were read thematically to identify recurring issues. A brief critical and comparative analysis was done to examine the frameworks of other countries to understand implementation of stronger enforcement and need for regulation. The purpose was to bring together law, policy, and cases in a way that shows where Indian judiciary stands, where it falls short, and what can be improved.

CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING OF AI IN JUDICIARY

Artificial intelligence (AI) is technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision making, creativity and autonomy. AI technologies used in courts are of different kinds from machine learning to predictive analytics. After the COVID-19 pandemic, the need of digitalisation gains a significant rise. Along with it comes AI to reduce the burden of courts from huge pending cases, paperless work and simplification of process.

Some of technology that judiciary currently using are:

a) SUVAS

In 2023, the Supreme Court of India launched an initiative to translate its extensive collection of 36,000 judgments into Scheduled Languages. The Supreme Court developed the Supreme Court Vidhik Anuvaad Software (SUVAS), which is an AI-enabled translator software, to encourage the use of regional languages in judicial processes like Assamese, Bengali, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Kashmiri, Khasi, Konkani, Malayali, Marathi, Nepali, Odia, Punjabi, Santali, Tamil, Telugu and Urdu. This innovative endeavour achieved significant success with the assistance of artificial intelligence and former judges of the High Court and legal secretaries.

b) SUPACE

The Supreme Court Portal Assistance in Court Efficiency (SUPACE), which is a software that intends to develop an application that is capable of understanding the case based on its factual matrix through intelligent searching of precedents along with recognition of cases, is currently undergoing trials. It is a system that collects relevant laws and information and presents them to the court.

c) Legal Research Analysis Assistant (LegRAA)

An AI based software tool namely Legal Research Analysis Assistant (LegRAA) has been developed under the guidance of eCommittee, Supreme Court of India, to aid judges in legal research, document analysis, and judicial decision support.

d) Digital Courts 2.1

It is an application being developed to assist judicial officers by providing access to integrated judgment databases, document management with annotations and automated drafting templates. Digital Courts 2.1 is equipped with voice-to-text feature (ASR - SHRUTI) and translation (PANINI) functionalities to assist the judges with order and judgment dictation.

e) AI Saransh

The Supreme Court of India is in the process of introducing an Artificial Intelligence (AI) tool known as AI Saransh. This tool, developed by the National Informatics Centre (NIC), is designed to generate precis or summaries of pleadings, streamlining the process of highlighting contentious issues in legal cases.

Along with these, many other AI initiatives are used like virtual courts, online database providing assistance, AI-based transcription (TERES), NyayKaushal (India's first ever e-Resource Centre and Virtual Court). In addition, the National

Legal Service Authority (NALSA) has launched an AI chatbot named 'LESA' for assisting litigants with application tracking services.

ADVANTAGES OF AI IN JUDICIARY

With the emergence of AI, judiciary has gain multiple benefits from introduction of e-Courts to hearing through video conferencing. The introduction of technology saves time and energy by reducing paper use in courtrooms, which can significantly reduce the environmental costs of the judicial and legal system, as files and documents are easier to transfer in less time and cost from one court to another. The use of AI has helped in addressing core challenges of backlogs, uneven access, linguistic barriers, reduce burden of pending cases along with new emerging cases and the heavy administrative load. AI has significantly transformed judicial working in India. It helps in speedier disposal of cases, efficient legal research, improved administrative functioning, easy accessibility and translation support.

CONSTITUTIONAL AND ETHICAL CHALLENGES

Despite being beneficial in field of judiciary, AI have many drawbacks. AI is being used to create fake cases and information taken is misappropriated. Cases cited do not exist in reality. Using AI in these circumstances too much without verification can lead to these instances entering the discussion legally unless reported or identified. This will mislead the judges and justice delivery will not be considered fair. The incident came up in *Greenopolis Welfare Association vs Narendar Singh and Ors*, where the petitioner challenged a trial court order restricting it from submitting a written statement. The Delhi High Court ordered the petition to be withdrawn in an order dated September 25, 2025, following the discovery of fake case citations. The petition also cited paragraphs 73 and 74 of *Raj Narain v. Indira Nehru Gandhi*, (1972), despite the judgment having only 27 paragraphs. These fabricated or misquoted precedents can harm the trust people have in the legal

system. Similarly, In the case of *Mata v. Avianca*, while it started off as a regular tort action filed against an airline company, it was soon elevated to be known as the best example of what can happen when lawyers employ artificial intelligence without validating their results. In a situation where two lawyers got penalized in 2023 for submitting a legal motion relying on six fabricated court decisions generated by ChatGPT, the perception of the use of artificial intelligence in law is significantly changed.

Further, using AI will leads to algorithmic biasness and discrimination resulting in violation Article 14. Discrimination on the basis of already given data as result will be given according to the existing scenario and input of system coding without consideration of new perspective like if white people centric data is provided to AI, result will always in favour of whites and against blacks or dark skin tone people. These biases in AI-systems can express in the form of racial, gender, ethnic, or cultural leanings, and can extend to other biases regarding to socioeconomic status, religion, caste, place of birth and more. Furthermore, it will harm due process of law resulting in unfair trials which will violate Article 21 of Constitution of India. Moreover, concerns related to data privacy and surveillance will arise. Data may be exposed through phishing, unauthorized data access, and other forms of server network weaknesses, leading to data integrity, information loss, and privacy invasion.

Sometimes, decisions are given on only on the basis of precedents and law but according to the current scenario of the society. Judges give judgement with considering all facts, moral reasoning and impact on public like Vishaka Guidelines were given later leading to POSH Act, 2023 after the case of *Visakha and Ors. v. State of Rajasthan* workplace sexual harassment as a violation of fundamental rights. AI lacks in human sensitivity and moral reasoning. It cannot create things that can bring changes in society valuing human emotions.

COMPARATIVE INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

Use of Artificial Intelligence is growing rapidly all over the globe. Integration of AI in judiciary leading to raise concerns over misuse. many countries have taken steps to regulate use of it. Some of these are:

a) South Korea

South Korea has achieved a milestone in AI regulations by enacting the first comprehensive law worldwide that regulates the safe implementation of AI technology. The Basic Act on the Development of Artificial Intelligence and the Establishment of a Foundation for Trustworthiness, or the AI Basic Act, came into force on January 22, 2026. The act mandates that companies be more responsible in addressing issues arising out of the use of generative AI technology. This includes labelling data generated using AI, providing prior notice about the use of generative AI or high-risk AI, and having human oversight when there is any such high risk involved.

b) European Union

The EU's Artificial Intelligence Act of 2024 placed AI systems under four categories and used a risk-based regulatory system. The use of certain types of AI, like manipulative AI and social scoring systems, is banned outright due to unacceptable levels of risks. AI systems posing significant risks require rigorous control and form the primary focus of the regulations. In order to ensure that the user knows he/she is dealing with an AI system, low-risk AI, like chatbots and deepfakes, must comply with transparency principles.

c) UNESCO Guidelines

The UNESCO Guidelines is made for the Application of AI in Tribunals and Courts. The UNESCO Guidelines for the Application of AI in Tribunals and Courts were officially presented at the roundtable meeting held in London on December 4, 2025. In order to aid organizations and individuals to design,

develop, buy, and implement AI technologies in a proper way, the UNESCO Guidelines contain 15 principles. Such principles are represented by human involvement and decision-making, auditability, and information security. In addition to that, suggestions regarding judicial authorities and single judges are provided. All such suggestions are related to actions to be taken by the court throughout the process of development of the AI technology. These rules set the standards for designing national and sub-national standards relevant to certain situations.

d) Canada

AI and Data Act (AIDA), proposed within the Digital Charter Implementation Act, 2022, will serve as the basis for designing, developing, and deploying AI systems that have an effect on Canadians.

e) Brazil

In March 2025, Brazil's National Council of Justice issued a resolution/guideline for the development, use and governance of AI solutions within the judiciary. The resolution sets out principles for the development, deployment and use of AI solutions by the judiciary.

SUGGESTIONS AND REFORMS

To deal such situation and save the principles of Constitution, use of AI in judiciary should be regulated. Ethical Guidelines should be made to avail the benefits of AI in field of judiciary and such guidelines should be mandatory to be followed. This will help to overcome misuse of AI until any legislation arrives. While using AI for judicial purpose, humans should overlook on its working and human oversight mechanism should be developed. Courts and all judicial

authorities must endeavour Courts and all judicial authorities must endeavour to design and sustain systems that ensure the safe storage of confidential information. Any user must not provide any legally protected, classified, or sensitive information in an artificial intelligence platform if it is not in the public domain. to design and sustain systems that ensure the safe storage of confidential information. Any user must not provide any legally protected, classified, or sensitive information in an artificial intelligence platform if it is not in the public domain. Proper judicial training and technological awareness can be done to avoid algorithmic biasness (clash between input and result given). In the fairness and equality framework of India, the AI system design and testing is required to be done in a manner that leads to an outcome which is fair, impartial, and non-discriminatory against anybody, especially the disadvantaged sections of society. The judicial system of India shall monitor the outcome generated by AI for any form of bias.

CONCLUSION

AI has considerably enhanced the performance of the Indian judiciary through legal research, translation, managing cases, and reducing administrative burdens. The development of projects such as SUVAS, SUPACE, and Virtual Courts clearly indicates the increasing role of technology in modernizing justice. But the increasing reliance on AI poses some major problems related to bias, privacy, transparency issues, and even undermines judicial discretion and human sensitivity. The process of providing justice can never be completely dependent on computerized programs as judicial decisions require a higher moral and constitutional framework and understanding of real-life situations. Thus, AI should be used only as an auxiliary technology, not as a substitute for human judges. Hence, India must devise suitable rules and policies regarding the use of AI technology within the legal system in order to uphold judicial conscience.

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